

Building on Stilts: A Mixed-use Development for Community Sustainability

*Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
the award of the degree of Bachelor of Architecture*

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DECLARATION

Dated: 07.06.2021

I Alemchila Tzudir, Scholar No. 2016BARC052 hereby declare that, the thesis titled '***Building on Stilts: A Mixed-use Development for Community Sustainability***', submitted by me in partial fulfilment for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Architecture at School of Planning and Architecture, Bhopal, India, is a record of bonafide work carried out by me. The design work presented and submitted herewith is my original work and I take sole responsibility for its authenticity. The matter/result embodied in this thesis has not been submitted to any other University or Institute for the award of any degree or diploma.

Alemchila Tzudir.

CERTIFICATE

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my gratitude to Prof. Sukanta Majumdar who has been patient and guided me through this thesis. Thank you Sir.

And to all the Professors who have taught me, thank you.

I am grateful to my friends and family for supporting me throughout this journey. Thank you Pepe for being my guiding Penguin, the Purane Neighbours and Meg-tan for the fun breaks, my siblings for being the minas and parents for well, everything.

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ABSTRACT

Urbanisation is a phenomenon that is synonymous to all growing cities, common characteristic features being – urban densification and urban sprawl. Urbanisation is unavoidable but unplanned agglomerations are.

This thesis project proposes a probable variation of planned urbanisation that is sensitive to the needs of the community and the site context. The thesis model follows the live-work-play concept of the mixed use development, whereby the living, working and recreational spaces are planned within walk able distances.

Keywords: Mixed-use; Green spaces; Stilts; Community; Sustainability

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

“Metropolitan cities will not come to balance until each one is small and autonomous enough to be an independent sphere of culture.” – (Christopher Alexander, 1977)

During the post war era when cities were recovering and modernisation set in, cities were segregated into zones which brought about the suburban trend. With the passing of decades it proved that the segregation was taking a toll on the lifestyle of the people, such that the distinction between the live and work spectrum was highlighted to the extent of, “the idea that work is toil, while only family time is ‘living’ –a schizophrenic view which creates tremendous problems for all the members of a family.” - (Christopher Alexander, 1977)

Cities today, regardless of scale therefore, strive to be an independent whole leading to the recurring propagation of the mixed use developments in the urban as well as the rural realm highlighting the *live work play (LWP)* concept.

The LWP concept is coherent with mixed use development and planning, holistic of the live, work and play spectrum. Thus, the two is concurrently weighed. The idea of a mixed use development is known to most but vaguely which implies ambiguity on the topic. (Herndon, 2011) But the definition given by the Urban Land Institute as characterized by – “three or more significant revenue-producing uses (such as retail/entertainment, office, residential, hotel, and/or civic/cultural/recreation) that in well planned projects are mutually supporting” (Schwanke, 2003) – reinforces that either two from the live, work, play spectrum constitutes the criteria of a mixed use development and entails the concept of LWP.

1.2 RATIONALE

“The emerging consensus is that development is more sustainable if it produces a mixture of uses. Segregation of land uses, encouraged in the past, is not relevant now. The trend back to mixed usage brings a number of potential benefits. It ensures vitality through activity and diversity. It makes areas safer. It also reduces the need to travel, making people less reliant on cars, bringing welcome environmental benefits. Diversity of uses adds to the vitality and interest of town centres. Different but complementary uses, during the day and in the evening can reinforce each other, making town centres more attractive to residents, businesses, shoppers and visitors” –John Gummer (DoE, 1995a).

Thus the implementation of the live, work, play concept on a community level will enable designing for the small and autonomous sphere of culture that will constitute the bigger picture of an independent city.

1.3 PROJECT INTENT

The intent of the Project is to design a Communal hub for A.G. Colony with Commercial, Retail, Housing and Recreational precincts through a Mixed-use development that will promote sustainable living.

1.4 PROJECT REQUIREMENTS

A mixed-use development that is sensitive to the needs of the people associated with A.G. Colony. It calls for a holistic development of the following precincts (with all necessary planning and architectural design drawings) –

1. Commercial *(20% of buildable area)*

Must include retail, eateries and studio spaces.

2. Housing *(30% of buildable area)*

A potpourri of studio apartments, 1BHK, 2BHK and 3BHK; each living unit with attached decks.

3. Public *(10% of buildable area)*

A community hall of strength 200 people and an open market development.

4. Recreational *(40% of buildable area)*

One common playground, jogging treks and parks.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

For literature review several guidelines, research papers, online sources and books as formulated in the table 1.1 have been referred to in order to understand the dynamics of *live, work, play* concept in theory to aid the research.

2016BARC052								
Seminar Leading to Thesis 2020								
Background Study								
S.No.	Reading Title	Aim/Intent	RQ	Objectives	Methods	Outcome	Remarks	Reference in APA style
1	The Architecture of Mixed Uses	to consider the bottom-up processes of the socio-economic conditions through architecture	Questions the extent to which economy and architecture work together	defining different types of spatial adaptability when commercial and residential use are combined	Case study, site study and analysis of maps	initiatives focused on bottom-up practices perceived by the community	portrayed how mixed use architecture works in small scale	Narvese, Laura B. Penn, Alan. (2016). The Architecture of Mixed Uses. <i>Journal of Space Syntax</i> , 7, 107-136.
2	Mixed Use Design Guidelines (City of Castle Pines, Colorado)	Prepared to supplement the Castle Pines Zoning Ordinance		sensitizing the citizens on the guidelines	Background and context, vision with guidelines		general idea of the intent for mixed use design in a city is clarified	Community Development Department (2018). <i>Mixed Use Design Guidelines</i> (City of Castle Pines, Colorado)
3	Challenges and Benefits of Mixed Use Buildings	to compare the pros and cons of mixed use buildings	what are the pros and cons of mixed use buildings?		Literature review		pros-max. land resources, reduce long term maintenance cost, constant evolution; cons-parking, noise, traffic	Nordine Commercial (2020). <i>Challenges and Benefits of Mixed Use Buildings</i> . https://nordinecommercial.com/challenges-and-benefits-of-mixed-use-buildings/
4	Mixed-Use Development in Theory and Practice: Learning from Atlanta's Mixed Experiences	Understanding the Theory and practices			Literature Study, Case Study		have a clearer picture of history and its context on mixed use development	Joshua D. Herndon (2011). <i>Mixed-Use Development in Theory and Practice: Learning from Atlanta's Mixed Experiences</i> .
5	A Pattern Language	to explore the concept of independent towns	the school of thought behind it		empirical		interesting theories	Christopher Alexander (1997). <i>A Pattern Language</i>

Figure 1: Literature Review

The Delaware Valley Regional Planning Commission, carried out a case study on five mixed use developments of different scale (neighbourhood to buildings, viz. Peekskill Art Tech Lofts 21, Walter Baker Lofts 23, Miles & Generalis Lofts 25, The Mills at East Falls 27, 249 A Street and 300 Summer Street) and drew conclusions from its results as follows –

2.1 BENEFITS OF LIVE/WORK (Commission, 2004)

- By living on the same property that one works, commuting is reduced.
- Live/work occupants may spend more time with and be closer to their families.
- Live/work allows flexibility in the time spent on different activities.
- A better balance of one's professional life and personal life can be achieved.
- Two professions can be handled more efficiently, for those who choose to pursue more than one employment in their live/work units.
- Occupants of live/work invest financially and emotionally into a community.
- Live/work tends to enliven communities by generating more foot traffic and activities.
- Live/work boosts the tax revenues and economic development of the communities where they are located.
- Live/work may serve as transitional development between residential areas and commercial and/or industrial areas.
- Live/work, by its nature, encourages environmental friendliness

Figure 2: Benefits of mixed-use development
(Source: Coupland 2007)

2.2 DRAWBACKS OF LIVE/WORK (Commission, 2004)

- Distractions may easily arise for some live/work occupants.
- Work may become a ceaseless occupation for some live/work occupants.
- Tenants of affordable live/work may risk the possibility of being priced out of their units.
- Live/work developments that crop up in industrial zones may end up displacing the primary use that was originally intended for these districts.
- Noises that are normally linked to the operations in industrial zones may become a source of complaint by new live/work occupants.
- Businesses operating from live/work units, on the other hand, may be a source of complaint by the pre-existing population of the district.
- As businesses conducted from dwelling units can be easily hidden from the general view of the public, a municipality needs to be diligent in its efforts to register these businesses and ensure their compliance to building and zoning codes.

CHAPTER 3 SITE CONTEXT

3.1 SITE LOCATION

The chosen site lies on the south-western tip of Kohima town in Lower A.G. Colony Kohima, Nagaland. It is one of the administrative centres of the capital, hosting five government offices (Accountant General Office, Power Department, P.H.E.D., Directorate of Agriculture, Veterinary Department and Directorate of Water and Soil Conservation) clubbed in one official hub. The site's prominent landmark is Model Christian College, an acclaimed college in Kohima.

Figure 3: Site Location

(Author, 2021)

3.2 SITE HISTORY

The main settlement in A.G. Colony, Kohima started with the establishment of A.G. Office Headquarters and its subsequent living quarters in 1973. By 1980, other state government offices were set up in its periphery, introducing more housing quarters for the government officials. By 1897, Model Christian College (then Model School) was established bringing in more opportunities for the economic sector to grow in the Colony. After a decade, by 2006-7 other private settlements sprawled round the valley. The garden spaces of the government quarters were not spared either, densifying the urban grain and leading to congestion.

Figure 4: Site History
(Author, 2021)

3.3 SITE CONNECTIVITY

The site has an overall good connectivity with three taxi stands stationed within 300 M radius of the site and access through the A.G. road on the Westside and Model School road on the North.

Figure 5: Site Connectivity
(Author, 2021)

Across the road on the North-East is Model Christian College and 100-300 m walk to the official hub on the Westside. On the South is a thick forest bordering Lerie Colony. It is surrounded by housing along the rest of the periphery.

3.4 SITE PROFILE

Area: 37,900 SQM

F.A.R.: 1.5

Ownership: Private

Site: Greenfield

The site is a buffer area catering to both the residential, commercial and administrative zone, giving it high potential of further development.

Figure 6: Zoning of Site Surroundings
(Author, 2021)

CHAPTER 4

A LIVE-WORK-PLAY RESEARCH OF SITE SURROUNDINGS

4.1 DATA COLLECTION

A background research on the site was conducted to aid the thesis and the data collection for this research was procured through primary and secondary sources, where the former is obtained through survey of people for a quantitative study using a questionnaire under the criteria that they satisfy either their live, work or play or two or all realms in the chosen precinct of study, that is, A.G. Colony. The latter is obtained through government offices and Google Earth for maps and demographics.

Figure 7: Form & Type of Data Collection
(Author, 2021)

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis has been done through two methods concurrently as shown in Fig.8

The Segregation is supported by two methods, one for the built/unbuilt space zoning and the other for understanding the people as -

Group A: *Live, work is satisfied within the colony premises*

Group B: *Only work is satisfied within the colony premises*

The data attained both qualitative and quantitative will then be analyzed to draw strategies to guide a 'live, work, play' development in a community level.

Figure 8: Methods of Analysis
(Author, 2021)

**Figure 9: Zoning Tabulation Result
(Author, 2021)**

4.2.1 LAND USE OBSERVATIONS

- The live (residential) and work (offices) in the precinct are easily identifiable but the play does not constitute proportionally to the scale of the community.
- Also observed that the school presents commercial opportunities but is underutilised.
- Open green cover is the dominant land use but due to its privatized ownership, it is not accessible to all.
- **Issues:** The colony is about 15 minutes' drive to the main town but due to congestion and traffic jams, it takes double or triple the time which is inconvenient for all commuters. Shortage of housing in the colony is immanent as the government quarters in the colony cannot cater to the demand which leaves commuting as the only solution. The presence of the college has brought business of hostels and paying guests to the people but again, studio apartments are naught. Small businesses like grocery shops thrive on small scale mixed use buildings but absence of eateries and necessities other than groceries are sought elsewhere. Though the colony has potential consumers and users, it is dependent on other colonies still.

4.2.2 LIVE WORK PLAY RELATIONSHIP

- A.G. and P.H.E.D. government quarters constitute of 37% approx. of the residential zone while 63% is used for people who are associated with A.G. Colony only in the 'live' realm.
- Since only two of the offices have their living quarters in the colony itself, the work/live percentage is 37% and 48% for the people who are engaged with the colony only in the 'work' realm.

- As the existing commercial and other activities constitute 0.4% of the whole precinct, a lack is observed due to which the 'play' realm partially engages all the live, work and live/work groups.

Figure 10: Percentage of LWP that corresponds to Live
(Author, 2021)

Figure 11: Percentage of LWP that corresponds to Work
(Author, 2021)

Thus, in order to continue further data collection and analysis of the precinct, segregation of two groups was seen necessary to understand views of people associated with the precinct in both the live and work realm and those associated only with the work realm.

Group A: *Live, work is satisfied within the colony premises*

Group B: *Only work is satisfied within the colony premises*

This would lead to a comparative analysis of users with different perspectives helping to analyse the relationship of live, work, play when integrated and differentiated within and outside the precinct.

The Questionnaire was circulated to a total of 50 people (25: Group A and 25: Group B) out of which 38 responses were received (25: Group A and 13: Group B) through internet and a few house to house visit for the older generation.

Note: Refer Index for the Comparative Analysis of Group A and Group B.

4.3 CONCLUSION

The following conclusions have been drawn considering the views of the majority.

Group A:

When live and work come together the commuting is reduced to about 11-20 minutes which allows more time for an individual to invest in their personal lives. The main means of commuting is walking which saves on carbon emission and economic expenditure. Further it is considered to have a positive impact on physical and mental health as it encourages one to be physically active which impacts the mental health as well.

The chosen precinct lacks the third element of LWP which is the Play spectre and this topples the balance that is otherwise achieved in the Live Work. With the inhabitants mostly attaining the Play by driving to other colonies increases the carbon emission and makes the precinct incompetent for an independent sphere.

Group B:

When the live and work are not stationed together, commuting takes more time of about 30-40 minutes or more and the means of commuting is motorised which adds to carbon emission and takes more time of the individuals and their personal lives. The physical and mental effect of commuting has more negativity, although the positive were not naught.

While all agreed for their work place to be near their living, the reason why they were not stationed so was majorly (61%) due to the reason that they were permanently settled elsewhere and this was found to be from the age of 50 upwards while the generation of 50 and below gave the reason of shortage in housing.

Summary:

The comparative analysis implies that the theory of live work play concept is not a full proof plan but co-relates with the practical ground and is feasible in general. The concept of LWP was also favoured by both Group A and B.

Through the live case study of the chosen precinct, it was observed that all three spectres of the live, work and play are equally important in order to achieve the benefits of the LWP dynamics.

Through the study of the maps it was seen that planning is one of the most important factor to allow for mixed use development where LWP is executed.

4.4 STRATEGIES

The following strategies have been drawn to guide a 'live, work, play' development in a community level as a concluding study for the paper –

1. All three spectres of the live, work and play should be incorporated and should be done so from the planning stage.
2. The LWP triangle should be within walk able distances, preferably 10-15 minutes (max.).
3. The Play spectre should be seen as a common ground and be planned and designed for all to access with ease.

The strategies formulated shall be applied in the thesis design and planning to achieve the benefits of a live-work-play environment for a sustainable community that shall strive to be an independent sphere of culture.

CHAPTER 5 SITE ANALYSIS

5.1 MACRO CLIMATE

Kohima has a humid subtropical climate - a pleasant and moderate climate. December and January are the coldest months when frost occurs and in higher altitudes, snowfall occasionally occurs. During peak summer months from July-August, temperature ranges an average of 80-90 Fahrenheit. Heavy rainfall occurs during summer.

Figure 13: Macro Climate
(Meteoblue, 2021)

Figure 12: Sun Path
(Author, 2021)

5.2 MICRO CLIMATE

Owing to the vegetation and stream on the site vicinity the temperature is comparatively cool throughout. Following the terrain of the site contours, the wind direction is more prominent on the South-West direction.

Figure 14: Micro Climate
(Author, 2021)

5.3 TOPOGRAPHY

The highest elevation on the site is at Level 4 (along A.G. Road) and lowest at Level -21 which is a difference of 57M. The contours cascade down from West to East in a steep slope which gradually eases halfway through to a gentler slope.

The slope is steepest at the area between A.G. Road and the Site Road and gentlest at the mid- point of the site.

Vegetation

The types of vegetation found in the site are - Bamboo, Mango trees, Cherry tree, Peach tree, Pines, gooseberry and other small shrubs like the philodendron gederacaem.

Figure 16: Site Vegetation

Figure 15: Site

(Author, 2021)

Slope Analysis

The slope percentage ranges from 8% to 67%. The steepest being on the Western Hill and the gradual being on the South-Western part which is comparatively plain.

Drainage

A small stream flows on the South-Western valley of the site where all the storm water is drained. The drainage within the site follows the natural contour that drains into the stream.

Soil

Inceptisols - fine loamy. The site soil comes under the moderately deep excessively drained fine soil on steeply sloping hill slope and valleys with moderate erosion as per the soil Map of Kohima District.

Figure 17: Site Topography
(Author, 2021)

5.4 SITE VISTAS

The terraced gardens are a prominent site character. It is the main element or foreground of vistas from all directions with vegetation as the middle-ground and the built form of the Colony as the background. The natural elements of the site imbue a rural touch hinting a closer relationship with nature. This is to the advantage of mental wellbeing (which is discussed in detail in Chapter 8).

Figure 18: Site Vistas (Author, 2021)

CHAPTER 6

CASE STUDY

For case study, four mixed use projects were undertaken to understand the conceptualising, planning and execution of mixed-use projects. Only the profile and leanings of the projects are discussed here.

6.1 CITY CENTRE

Figure 19: City Center Perspective view

(The Plan, 2018)

Client: Thakker Developers

Completion Date: 05/2020

Site Area: 23,361.34 Sqm

Gross Floor Area: 54385 Sqm

Costs (\$): 1896264

Architects: Sanjay Puri Architects

Climate: tropical, wet and dry climate; highest 30.7°C in summer and lowest 18.5°C in winter

Main learning: Area Programming + Form Development

- Fragmentation / modulation of the form creation organises the area programming
- Terrace gardens can atone as green areas for the built area of the plot
- Climate analysis has been applied throughout the concept and design process; thus partaking in shaping the built form to its advantage
- Identity of building sought
- Segregation of motor and pedestrian movement
- Strategic placement of service core along the periphery of built form
- Play in levels invites more people while making more levels accessible.
- Main entry point via. the core allows more interaction and participation of the built, unbuilt and the users.

DESIGN PROCESS

Figure 20: Design Process

(The Plan, 2018)

Figure 21: Design Development

(The Plan, 2018)

6.2 THE TREES

City: Mumbai

Client: Godrej

Completion Date: 2013

Site Area: 34 Acres (1,37,593 Sqm)

Architects: Sasaki

Climate: tropical, wet and dry climate; highest 34°C in summer and lowest 17°C in winter

Figure 22: Schematic view showing function

(Sasaki, 2013)

Figure 23: Site Plan

(Sasaki, 2013)

Main learning: Planning

- The grid planning accounts for the systematic setting of the site.
- The street as corridors amasses huge areas that can be used for interactive and recreational spaces.
- These corridors act as a buffer or space of interchanging from work to live and vice versa; thus play spectre bridging the live-work spectres.
- Vehicular movement is limited promoting more foot traffic

- The service lane is at the periphery of the site
- While the play spectre is distributed via. the corridors, the core of it is still at the centre wrapped adjacent to the live spectre at one side and work at the other.

Figure 24: Bird's Eye View
(Sasaki, 2013)

Figure 25: Sense of Community
(Sasaki, 2013)

6.3 SHANGHAI GREENLAND CENTRE

City: Shanghai

Client: Shanghai Greenland Group Co., Ltd.

Completion Date: 2017

Site Area: 20,000 Sqm

Gross Floor Area: 3,04,910 Sqm

Architects: Nikken Sekkei

Climate: humid subtropical climate; highest 32°C in summer and lowest 1°C in winter

Figure 26: Site Plan of Shanghai Greenland Center

(ArchDaily, 2018)

Main learning: Landscape

- The terraced garden cum. park spans the whole roof but all levels of it are accessible from outside without having to enter the building. A park truly open to the public.
- The transit points were also incorporated into the design as urban corridors, having a strong public character.
- Playful level play

Figure 28: Urban Park
(ArchDaily, 2018)

Figure 27: Perspective View
(ArchDaily, 2018)

6.4 BOSCO VERTICALE

City: Milan

Completion Date: 2014

Built Area: 50,000 Sqm

Architects: Boeri Studio

Climate: moderately continental; highest 30°C in summer and lowest 2°C in winter

Main learning: Terrace Gardening

- The cantilevered terraced gardens are designed to regulate the micro-climate of the apartments.
- About the plant containers – “Depending on the plant the dimensions of the containers are: in the case of a tree, 1.10 metres deep and 1.10 metres wide; in the case of shrubs and bushes, a minimum 0.5 metres’ depth and 0.5 metres’ width was specified.

The structure of the containers is entirely protected with bituminous waterproofing membrane against root penetration. Along the interior surfaces

Figure 5. Typical plan showing the terraces cantilevered from the main tower plans. © Stefano Boeri Architetti

Figure 6. Detail section showing cantilevered terraces. © Stefano Boeri Architetti

Figure 29: Typical Plan and Section
(Giacomello, 2015)

of the plant container is a layer of separation and drainage made of two synthetic non-woven filters with a three-dimensional filament core. This layer has a drain structure with high suction capacity to ensure optimal drainage of possible out-flowing water.” (Giacomello, 2015)

Figure 31: View into a plant container with membrane and protective sheeting
(Giacomello, 2015)

Figure 30: View
(Giacomello, 2015)

CHAPTER 7

A RESEARCH ON THE IMPACT OF MENTAL WELLBEING OF THE INHABITANTS IN ASSOCIATION WITH GREEN SPACES

The following research was undertaken to supplement the thesis design development in order to understand the impact of green spaces on the mental wellbeing of the inhabitants and inculcate the finding to use green spaces as a design element in the project.

Note: Only the findings of the research are discussed here.

7.1 SUMMARY

This research paper studies the relationship between *green spaces* and the *mental wellbeing* of the inhabitants by assessing the impact of the former on the later. The research is a corollary of the Shinrin-yoku concept of forest watching that has been proven to benefit the mental wellbeing and behaviour of an individual.

“Ulrich’s Stress Reduction Theory (SRT) proposes that contact with unthreatening natural environments or viewing natural elements, having a restorative effect can be effective in reducing stress creating positive emotions and feelings.” (Townsend, 2014)

7.2 FINDINGS

These findings have been drawn after analysing the data collected from the survey questionnaire that recorded 99 responses.

Finding 1:

Figure 32: Mental Wellbeing Index and Green Space Influence

(Author, 2021)

The influence of an inhabitant’s association with green spaces undeniably affects their mental wellbeing in ways of reducing stress such as making them feel ‘cheerful in good spirits, calm and relaxed, active and vigorous, fresh and rested’ (from WHO-5 survey).

Figure 32 shows the Mental Wellbeing Index as recorded of inhabitants associated with private, shared and public green spaces and its leverage on the influence on the mental wellbeing of the inhabitant. It shows that the **association is above 50% on all three spatial hierarchies thus establishing the evident influence.**

Finding 2:

Figure 33: Inhabitant's Association with Green Spaces

(Author, 2021)

The second finding as shown in Figure 33 is the association of the inhabitants with green spaces plotted against the frequency of their engagement.

The shared green space shows the most positive engagement of the inhabitants as their engagement ranges from *many times a day* to *rarely in a week* with *sometimes in a month* and *never* at nil. This is followed by the private green spaces with maximum engagement in terms of frequency.

Finding 3:

Figure 34: Frequency against Mental Wellbeing Index

(Author, 2021)

The third finding as shown in Figure 34 establishes the relation that the more frequency in association with the green spaces, the higher is the Mental Wellbeing Index of the inhabitants.

7.3 LEARNING

The role of a designer while designing green spaces then would be to analyse the available hierarchy of green spaces and to plan and design such that it encourages the association of inhabitants with green spaces to boost their mental health and reduce their stress levels. These spaces may follow a spatial hierarchy to address different needs from private spaces to shared and public spaces.

CHAPTER 8 CONCEPT

The aim is to design a sustainable project that promotes economic, social and environmental sustainability of a community using the mixed-use principles of the live-work-play. The project is not intended to be a gated development but rather a panacea to the facilities that the Colony lacks.

Figure 35: Mixed use Development for Community Sustainability

(Author, 2021)

8.1 DEFINITIONS

“Sustainable communities meet the diverse needs of existing and future residents, their children and other users, contribute to a high quality of life and provide opportunity and choice. They achieve this in ways that make effective use of natural resources, enhance the environment, promote social cohesion and inclusion and strengthen economic prosperity.” Egan Review

“Mixed-use developments are those with three or more significant revenue-producing uses (such as retail/entertainment, office, residential, hotel, and/or civic/cultural/recreation) that in well planned projects are mutually supporting” Urban Land Institute.

8.2 CONCEPT RATIONALE

The concept rationale is derived from the penchant to preserve the strong characteristic features of the site, that is, the existing terraced gardens and the vegetation, for which the buildable area of the site was mapped with respect to vegetation and slope analysis. On overlaying the two maps the final buildable area was restricted as shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: Concept Rationale

(Author, 2021)

The location of which was neither ideal nor feasible as it has no road access and compromised on the existing terraced gardens.

8.3 CONCEPT INVENTORY

This brought about the idea of building on stilts which would not only remove the constrain set on buildable area but also preserve the natural terrain by avoiding site grading. This allowed co-existing with the natural terrain of the site and save as much vegetation leading to the inhabitants' increased association with green spaces.

Thus, the three main design inventories that guide the whole thesis design were formulated as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Design Inventory

(Author, 2021)

A. Design Inventory A: Building on Stilts –

It allows retaining the natural terrain of the site with minimum intervention. Additionally, through effective planning the existing vegetation of the site can be preserved. Thereby, removing the restriction on buildable slopes and area.

B. Design Inventory B: Traditional Naga Hut Layout

Following the layout of a typical Naga hut layout assures that each living unit is connected to an open space that is via. a deck which can be used as green terraces or for rejuvenation. (Private and shared green spaces)

C. Design Inventory C: Traditional Naga Village Layout

Traditional Naga village layouts of hilly regions often followed the planning as shown in Figure 37-C whereby every living unit had street access which were vertically connected through a series of steps, drawing a strong visual connect within the clusters.

8.4 CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT

The concept has been developed as shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Concept Development

(Author, 2021)

The stilts continue as columns on the superstructure and piles in the substructure as per design inventory A. The banding by beam ties the columns together ensuring stability.

The cantilevered beams support the corridors that act as streets of the living units as per design inventory C. Similarly, the deck is supported as well. The living unit comes in between with access to both sides following the layout design inventory B. The module thus formulated allows direct plumbing through the floor, indicating that the service areas be preferably placed towards the corridors.

Iterating this module with reference to design inventory C, creates the visual and functional imagery of the typical traditional Naga settlement with the private decks and steps interlinking the levels.

8.5 STRUCTURE AND MATERIAL

The load bearing structural frame is laid out in steel I-sections that are bolted and the non-load bearing walls and floors are of pre-fabricated concrete blocks. The roof is held by welded hollow steel sectioned rafters and king truss. (Figure 39)

Figure 39: Conceptual Structure and material rationale

(Author, 2021)

CHAPTER 9 SITE ZONING

9.1 ZONING

The site zoning has been planned with respect to the site surroundings – the Official hub on the Westside, the school on the North and the existing road connection as shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Zoning Process

(Author, 2021)

The Retail zoning is stationed along the road especially focused on the area abutting the A.G. Road as it has better access to the official hub, while the residential with part retail is planned along the existing site road. This gives a wide area for developing the recreation or play area.

Figure 41: Site Zoning

(Author, 2021)

Figure 42: Site Plan
(Author, 2021)

9.2 DRAINAGE

The drainage in the site has been designed along the contours to retain water in two reservoirs – one underground where the rain water that is harvested would be stored and then other where the overflow of the underground tank and the site runoff would be stored in a pond. The overflow of this would then finally drain off in the existing stream on the site periphery.

In the entire site, the only grading has been done on level -6 for Playground 2 with the underground water reservoir beneath and the other being the parking for the housing clusters on Level -5 with the septic tank (ST1) underneath.

Figure 43: Site Drainage
(Author, 2021)

Figure 44: Site Summary
(Author, 2021)

CHAPTER 10

CLUSTER PLANNING

Applying the learnings from the case studies and researches that were conducted, the project developed the following clusters –

1. Retail Cluster 1

It consists of an eatery, retail stores, an inn and a gym – aimed to cater the needs of the Colony inhabitants, additionally aimed at the potential customers from the official hub.

2. Housing Cluster 1, 2 and 3

The Housing Clusters are designed with convenient stores and an eatery at the top level for the inhabitants in the clusters, additionally aimed at the potential customers from the College due to its ease in direct accessibility.

3. Community Hall

The Community Hall is designed for the communal functions that take place in the Colony such as Pre-Christmas programmes etc. This facility can also create revenue by renting it out for commercial or private occasions.

A conference hall for the Colony Panchayat has also been attached with a spacious porch that overlooks Playground 2.

4. Gazebo 1, 2

Gazebo 1 is a 7M radius pavilion that can be used for open exhibitions and markets while Gazebo 2 is of 3.5M designed and placed along the jogging path as rest and communal spaces for the community.

10.1 CONNECTIVITY

The interconnectivity of the clusters with reference to Design Inventory B and C (Figure 37), is such that each floor has direct access to the road and vertical connectors interlinking the levels with the road. The parking for retail has been incorporated within the building structure but parking for housing clusters has been designed on the base at level -5. (Figure 45)

Figure 45: Horizontal & Vertical Cluster Connectivity Map

(Author, 2021)

10.2 AREA PROGRAMMING

COMMERCIAL									
UNIT	PARKING (SQM)	TOILET	AREA (SQM)	NO.	TOTAL AREA (SQM)	LEVEL	CORRIDORS & STAIRWAY	FLOOR TOTAL (SQM)	
1 Eatery 1		1	97.3	1	97.3	5	12.2	97.3	
2 Convenient Store 1		1	100	1	100				
3 Retail Store Type A	138		14	2	28	4			266
4 Retail Store Type B			32	1	32				
5 Retail Store Type C			22	5	110				
6 Retail Store Type D			32	1	32				
7 Public Toilet	141		2.3	4	9.2	3	355	679.2	
8 Inn	23.6	5	281	1	281	2	15.6	320.2	
9 Convenient Store 2	68		77	1	77				
10 Convenient Store 3			69	1	69				
11 Eatery 2	140	1	54.5	1	54.5	0	46.2	454.7	
12 Retail 3+4			60	2	120		8	128	
13 Office		2	53.6	1	53.6	-1	41	94.6	
TOTAL RETAIL AREA								2040	

Table 2: Area Programming of Commercial Zone

(Author, 2021)

HOUSING									
	UNIT	TOILET	DECK (SQM)	AREA (SQM)	NO.	TOTAL AREA (SQM)	LEVEL	CORRIDORS	FLOOR TOTAL (SQM)
1	Studio Apartment A	1	12	54	5	330	-1	191	521
2	3BHK	3	30	122.7	3	458.1	-2	88	546.1
3	DUPLEX 3BHK	3	32	111	4	572			
4	1BHK	1	15	48	1	63	-3	282	917
5	Studio Apartment B	1	16	32	1	48			
6	2BHK	2	16	80	2	192			
7	2BHK	2	16	102	2	236			
8	1BHK Type B	1	20	42.6	2	125.2	-4	373	974.2
9	Studio Apartment C	1	16	19	1	35			
10	1BHK Type C	1	16	40	2	112	-5	178	325
11	Stairway					350			350
12	Parking					330			330
Total number of Units					23				
TOTAL HOUSING AREA									3963.3

Table 3: Area Programming of Residential Zone

(Author, 2021)

PUBLIC									
	UNIT	TOILET	DECK (SQM)	AREA (SQM)	NO.	TOTAL AREA (SQM)	LEVEL	CORRIDORS	FLOOR TOTAL (SQM)
1	Community Hall		81	109	1	190	-4	54	190
2	Conference Hall	2		55	1	55	-5	42	55
3	Shed			60	1	60			
4	Gazebo 1			180	1	180	-6		240
5	Gazebo 2			52	4	208			208
6	Stairway			13.5	1	13.5			13.5
TOTAL PUBLIC AREA									706.5

RECREATION			
	UNIT	LEVEL	AREA (SQM)
1	Playground 1	-6	1290
2	Playground 2	-7	1500
3	Natural Terraced gardens		6200
4	Jogging Trek		1140
TOTAL RECREATION AREA			10130

Table 4: Area Programming of Public and Recreation Zone

(Author, 2021)

**CHAPTER 11
FINAL DRAWINGS**

Figure 46
(Author, 2021)

Figure 47
 (Author, 2021)

Figure 48

(Author, 2021)

Figure 49
 (Author, 2021)

Figure 50
(Author, 2021)

Figure 51
(Author, 2021)

Figure 53: View of Retail Cluster 1 from A.G. Road

Figure 52: Eatery

Figure 55: View of Corridor and stairs

Figure 54: View of open space for vendors from retail store

Figure 57: Entryway to the Inn

Figure 56: View of dining space (Inn)

Figure 58: View of Retail Cluster 1 connected to Site Road @lvl 0

Figure 59
(Author, 2021)

Figure 60
(Author, 2021)

Figure 61
 (Author, 2021)

Figure 62
(Author, 2021)

Figure 63
(Author, 2021)

Figure 64
(Author, 2021)

Figure 65
(Author, 2021)

SECTION 3 - HC1 + HC2

Figure 66

(Author, 2021)

Figure 67: Terrace stacking

(Author, 2021)

Figure 69: View of Retail Store on Housing Cluster 2

Figure 68: View of Retail Store on Housing Cluster 1

Figure 71: Interior View of Dining spaces

Figure 70: View of Open Dining on Housing Cluster 1

Figure 73: Interior view of Studio Apartment

Figure 72: View of Office from Terrace Garden in Housing Cluster 1

Figure 75: Interior View of Bedroom 3BHK

Figure 74: Interior view of 2BHK Duplex

(Author, 2021)

Figure 77: Interior view of Bedroom 1BHK

Figure 76: Shared Garden spaces

Figure 78: Vertical connectors as Communal Spaces

Figure 80: Typical view of connecting corridors

Figure 79: Vertical connectors as Communal Spaces

Figure 81: Direct connection of apartments from site road

Figure 82
(Author, 2021)

Figure 83
(Author, 2021)

Figure 84
 (Author, 2021)

Figure 85

(Author, 2021)

Figure 86

(Author, 2021)

Figure 88: Entryway to Community Hall

Figure 87: View of Community Hall

Figure 90: View of Housing Cluster 3

Figure 89: View of Community Hall

Figure 91: View of Gazebos

Figure 92: View of the build forms

(Author, 2021)

Figure 93: Birds' Eye View of Site from A.G. Road

Figure 94: Site view from Jogging trek on the Western side

(Author, 2021)

CHAPTER 12

CONCLUSION

The thesis has developed in close relationship to the live-work-play concept by addressing the needs of the community, that is, the inhabitants of A.G. Colony and those associated with it. The playgrounds, communal spaces, jogging treks and preserved terraced gardens account for the lack of play spaces for recreation of the Community. The platform to expand commercially has also been addressed through retail stores, eateries, an inn and a gym to curb the needs of the inhabitants within the Colony premises such that driving to other Colonies to procure such needs is avoided. Lastly housing has been added in answer to shortage of housing in the Colony, the target users being college students and office workers from the official hub.

The design of all these elements was guided with the concept to preserve the site characteristic features –the terrain and vegetation. This was achieved through the three design inventories of *Building with Stilts*, the traditional layout of a *Naga Hut* and *Village*.

Additionally, the project has achieved increased association of inhabitants with *Green Spaces* though the design of every unit having direct access to a deck with a terrace garden; the preserved vegetation of the site allows the *shirin-yoku* concept to manifest. As per research, this shall have a positive effect on mental wellbeing of the inhabitants.

In conclusion, it can be said that the thesis project is a *Mixed-use Development for Community Sustainability*.

Further Work: The project can entail further study on grounds of structural analysis.

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INDEX

SEMINAR LEADING TO THESIS:

The Concept of Live, Work, Play: Assessment at Community Level

